

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 63(2) (2025) 68-81

EISSN 2543-5426

Water Quality Modeling for Pollution Assessment and Management of the Asa River, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study applied a one-dimensional water quality model using HEC-RAS and RAS Mapper to assess the pollution status of the Asa River in Ilorin, Nigeria. Field samples were collected at four stations during both dry and wet seasons and analyzed for physicochemical and nutrient parameters. Hydrodynamic simulation revealed that the river depth ranged from 0.32 m downstream to 9.80 m upstream, with velocities between 0.06 and 2.68 m/s. Water quality modeling indicated persistent low dissolved oxygen (3.9 - 5.2 mg/L) across stations, below the 6.5 mg/L ecological threshold, suggesting oxygen stress. Nutrients showed seasonal variability, with nitrates declining in the wet season due to dilution, while nitrite (0.206 - 0.274 mg/L) and organic phosphorus (>1.0 mg/L) exceeded international guidelines, indicating a risk of eutrophication. Model calibration showed good agreement between observed and simulated values, with minor deviations in organic nitrogen and phosphorus. The results show that the Asa River is unsuitable for domestic use without treatment and emphasize the need for stricter effluent control and sustainable river management.

Keywords: HEC-RAS, Asa River, Hydrodynamic Simulation, Water Quality Modeling, Seasonal Variation

1. INTRODUCTION

Rivers are vital freshwater resources that support domestic supply, agriculture, fisheries, and industrial development. However, rapid urbanization and industrialization in developing countries have intensified river pollution, threatening aquatic ecosystems and human health. In

Nigeria, many rivers receive untreated effluents, sewage, and runoff, leading to nutrient enrichment, oxygen depletion, and the spread of waterborne diseases [1, 2].

The Asa River in Ilorin, Kwara State, is a major water source for domestic and industrial uses. Previous studies have reported significant deterioration in its quality due to inputs from industries, abattoirs, and municipal discharges [4, 12]. Although some water quality assessments have been carried out, most relied on point sampling and did not incorporate hydrodynamic modeling, limiting their ability to predict pollutant transport under varying flow conditions.

This study therefore develops and applies a coupled hydrodynamic–water quality model using HEC-RAS to evaluate the current state of the Asa River. By integrating field data, laboratory analysis, and secondary datasets, the study assesses seasonal variations in key parameters and evaluates compliance with ecological and drinking water standards. The outcomes provide a scientific basis for effective pollution control and management strategies for the river basin.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Water quality refers to the physical, chemical, and biological attributes of water, which collectively determine its suitability for human, agricultural, and ecological uses [15]. Changes in water quality and distribution networks have significant implications for environmental sustainability, influenced greatly by anthropogenic sources such as industrial discharge and agricultural runoff.

These sources introduce pollutants like heavy metals, pesticides, and nutrients into water bodies, altering their natural composition and affecting aquatic life [15].

Water quality modeling is indispensable in managing aquatic environments, especially in the face of increasing anthropogenic pressures and climate change. These models allow scientists and policymakers to forecast how water bodies respond to various stressors, such as urbanization, industrial activities, and agricultural runoff, which are major contributors to surface water pollution [3]. By predicting the outcomes of such stressors, models provide a basis for developing mitigation strategies that aim to protect water resources and maintain ecosystem health.

Another key advantage of water quality modeling is its ability to integrate various data sources, including hydrological, chemical, and biological parameters. By integrating hydrological, chemical, and biological data, models capture the complex interactions that influence water quality. This integrated approach improves prediction accuracy and supports evidence-based policy decisions [9].

Hydrologic Engineering Center-River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) is software used for hydraulic and hydrology modeling. It can compute one-dimensional (1D) steady flow, two-dimensional (2D) unsteady flow, sediment transport, or a movable bed, as well as model water temperature or water quality [17]. This tool is essential for modeling water flow and assessing flood risks. Additionally, it supports water quality modeling, enabling the analysis of pollutants and their dispersion within river systems to enhance flood studies and determine vulnerable flood zones [8]. Recent advances in hydrological modeling tools, such as the Hydrologic Engineering Center's River Analysis System (HEC-RAS), provide opportunities to simulate river hydraulics and pollutant dynamics with improved accuracy.

HEC-RAS has been successfully applied in water quality studies of rivers in Ethiopia [16], Pakistan [22], and Nigeria [6]. However, its application to the Asa River remains limited.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3. 1. Study Area

The Asa River (Figure 1) flows through Ilorin, the capital city of Kwara State, Nigeria. Ilorin is geographically situated at approximately latitude 8°30'N and longitude 4°35'E, covering an area of about 100 km² with a population of over 800,000 inhabitants [21].

The region experiences a humid tropical climate characterized by two distinct seasons: a wet season from April to October and a dry season from November to March. The mean annual rainfall is about 1150 mm, while average temperatures range between 25 °C and 29 °C. Relative humidity typically varies from 65% to 80% [10].

Study Area (Inset: Map of Nigeria)

Figure 1. The Asa River - study area.

3. 2. Study Area and Sampling Stations

Four sampling stations (Table 1) were selected along the Asa River to capture spatial variations in water quality. Station 1 (Asa Dam) represented upstream conditions; Station 2 (Unity/Tuyil discharge point) received pharmaceutical effluents; Station 3 (Emir's Road) reflected midstream conditions influenced by urban runoff; and Station 4 (Amilengbe) represented the downstream reach, where cumulative impacts are most evident as it receives higher refuse loads from upstream.

Table 1. Geographic location of sampling stations in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Sampling Station	Name	Longitude	Latitude
1	Asa dam	4.560292°	8.451694°
2	Tuyil (yidi road)	4.554972°	8.477254°
3	Emirs Rd	4.560902°	8.487927°
4	Amilengbe	4.564393°	8.494128°

3. 3. Field Data Collection

Water samples were collected monthly over an eight-month period covering both the dry season (November 2024 – February 2025) and the wet season (April – July 2025). At each station (Figure 2(a,b)), samples were taken just below the water surface using sterilized 2.5 L plastic bottles between 08:00 and 16:00 hours. In situ measurements included temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), organic Nitrogen, nitrate, nitrite and organic phosphorous. Samples were transported under cold storage for laboratory analysis of nutrients and oxygen demanding substances.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2(a,b). Fieldwork activity at one of the sampling stations.

3. 4. Laboratory Analysis

Standard methods were employed for laboratory determinations. Dissolved oxygen was analyzed using the Winkler titrimetric method, while biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) was obtained as the difference between initial and final DO after a five-day incubation at 20 °C. Nutrient concentrations were analyzed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer: nitrates at 220 and 275 nm, nitrites at 543 nm, and phosphates at their respective absorption wavelengths. Organic nitrogen and organic phosphorus were determined following standard digestion and spectrophotometric procedures.

3. 5. Secondary Data Acquisition

Secondary datasets were integrated to strengthen the model inputs. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) data were obtained from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) for geometric profile generation. Discharge and hydrological records were sourced from published literature, while meteorological data (precipitation, temperature, wind speed, pressure, and humidity) were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet) at Ilorin Airport for the study period.

3. 6. Hydraulic Modeling

(a)

(b)

Figure 3(a,b). (a) River flow path,crosssection, River bank, (b) Unsteady flow boundary condition.

The river's geometry was generated in RAS Mapper and imported into HEC-RAS. River centerlines and banks were digitized, and 200 cross-sections (Figure 3a) were extracted at 50–100 m intervals along the study reach. Manning's roughness coefficients of 0.035 (channel) and 0.045 (overbanks) were adopted, based on field observations and [6]. Unsteady flow (Figure 3a) conditions were applied, with the upstream boundary defined by a flow hydrograph from

[13] and the downstream boundary specified as a normal depth with a slope of 0.0008 [14] (Figure 3b).

3. 7. Water Quality Modeling

The water quality module (Figure 4b) of HEC-RAS was activated to simulate temperature, dissolved oxygen, nutrients, and oxygen-demanding substances.

Observed field data at Asa Dam and Amilengbe were used as boundary conditions, while additional parameters such as algae, ammonium, CBOD, and phosphate were obtained from published studies [11, 16].

A dispersion coefficient of 25.6 m²/s [9] was applied to the reach. Meteorological datasets were integrated to account for atmospheric influences. Calibration and validation were carried out by comparing observed and simulated data using error metrics such as root mean square error (RMSE).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4(a,b). (a) Unsteady flow Simulation window, (b) HECRAS Water quality model simulation window.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4. 1. Hydraulic Simulation

The hydrodynamic model showed variations in depth and velocity along the Asa River. The maximum channel depth (9.80 m) occurred at the upstream section near Asa Dam, while the minimum depth (0.32 m) was recorded at Amilengbe downstream. Velocity also varied, with the highest value of 2.68 m/s observed upstream and the lowest value of 0.06 m/s downstream. These results are consistent with earlier studies [12], which reported maximum velocities of 2.16 m/s and depths between 0.96 and 9.74 m, confirming the reliability of the present model.

4. 2. Water Quality Simulation – Dry Season

During the dry season (Tables 2 and 3), observed and simulated values of temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), and nutrients showed strong consistency, indicating that the model was able to capture seasonal patterns effectively. At Asa Dam, DO was 4.70 mg/L, closely matched by the simulated value of 4.71 mg/L. This moderate DO concentration reflects relatively stable

conditions upstream, though lower flow rates in the dry season can reduce reaeration. At Emir’s Road, organic nitrogen was 0.0056 mg/L, again closely reproduced by the model (0.0059 mg/L). The low concentration suggests limited organic nitrogen inputs at this station, though the stability of nitrate values across stations (0.456 - 0.481 mg/L) indicates that nitrates remain an important nutrient source throughout the system. Nitrite concentrations, however, ranged from 0.206 to 0.259 mg/L and tended to increase downstream. This pattern may point to incomplete nitrification or contributions from municipal effluents, which are more concentrated when dilution capacity is reduced in the dry season.

Table 2. Average Observed and simulated data of water quality parameters during the dry season.

Sample Station	Observed data			Simulated output data		
	Temperature (°C)	Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	Organic Nitrogen (mg/L)	Temperature (°C)	Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	Organic Nitrogen (mg/L)
Asa Dam	27.650	4.700	0.0028	27.669	4.714	0.00279
Unity	28.100	5.175	0.0028	28.012	5.226	0.00279
Emirs road	27.725	4.925	0.0056	27.940	4.998	0.00594
Amilengbe	28.025	4.725	0.0028	27.865	4.853	0.00283

Table 3. Average Observed and simulated data of water quality parameters during the dry season.

Sample Station	Observed data			Simulated output data		
	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Organic Phosphorous (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Organic Phosphorous (mg/L)
Asa Dam	0.4808	0.2214	1.0513	0.4814	0.2219	1.0574
Unity	0.4618	0.2590	1.080	0.4605	0.2494	1.0576
Emirs road	0.4568	0.2237	1.1225	0.4574	0.2205	1.0583
Amilegbe	0.4592	0.2063	1.105	0.4587	0.2251	1.0608

Organic phosphorus exceeded 1.0 mg/L at all stations, with Unity recording the highest value of 1.08 mg/L. Elevated phosphorus concentrations are a major concern, as they indicate

a strong potential for eutrophication. The downstream enrichment likely results from a combination of industrial discharges, municipal wastewater, and domestic effluents, which accumulate due to reduced flow and limited dilution capacity during the dry season [3]. Similar observations have been made in other urbanized basins, where phosphorus loading remains a key driver of water quality degradation during low flow periods.

Concentrations downstream underscore the role of anthropogenic inputs in shaping dry-season water quality. The close match between observed and simulated data suggests that the model provides a reliable representation of seasonal dynamics, but the nutrient patterns highlight the need for better management of effluent discharges, particularly in urban areas.

4. 3. Water Quality Simulation – Wet Season

During the wet season (Tables 4 and 5), water temperature increased slightly, ranging from 29.0 to 29.7 °C, which may be attributed to higher ambient temperatures and reduced shading effects from increased surface water movement. Dissolved oxygen (DO) decreased further, reaching as low as 3.9 mg/L at Asa Dam and Unity. The decline in DO is consistent with stormwater inflows carrying organic matter and suspended solids, which increase biochemical oxygen demand and reduce reaeration capacity.

Nitrate concentrations fell sharply to 0.055 - 0.070 mg/L, reflecting dilution effects caused by heavy rainfall that reduced ion concentrations in the reservoirs. In contrast, nitrite values remained relatively high (0.229 - 0.274 mg/L). This persistence suggests incomplete nitrification or inputs of reduced nitrogen compounds during runoff events, as reported in similar studies [4].

Organic phosphorus levels exhibited the widest variation. At Unity, the lowest observed concentration was 0.128 mg/L, while the model predicted a higher value of 0.364 mg/L. This overestimation highlights the limitations of the model in simulating phosphorus dynamics under variable hydrological conditions. Fluctuations in phosphorus may also be influenced by storm-driven inputs such as soil erosion, domestic waste, and organic debris, which are commonly noted in tropical catchments during rainfall events.

Table 4. Average Observed and simulated data of water quality parameters during the wet season.

Sample Station	Observed data			Simulated output data		
	Temperature (°C)	Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	Organic Nitrogen (mg/L)	Temperature (°C)	Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)	Organic Nitrogen (mg/L)
Asa Dam	29.050	3.9	0.016807	29.3557	3.8613	0.00165
Unity	29.100	3.9	0.001401	29.7549	3.9692	0.00141
Emirs road	29.025	3.96	0.002241	30.2066	3.9573	0.002251
Amilegbe	29.125	4.5	0.002241	29.9293	4.4809	0.00221

Table 5. Average Observed and simulated data of water quality parameters during the dry season.

Sample Station	Observed data			Simulated output data		
	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Organic Phosphorous (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Organic Phosphorous (mg/L)
Asa Dam	0.05528	0.2295	0.5590	0.05562	0.2266	0.6883
Unity	0.07028	0.2713	0.1280	0.06957	0.2737	0.3638
Emirs road	0.05893	0.2740	0.0425	0.05894	0.2716	0.0578
Amilegbe	0.06532	0.2518	0.0578	0.06530	0.2533	0.0381

4. 4. Model Calibration and Validation

The model demonstrated satisfactory performance, with observed and simulated values showing close agreement. Deviations were generally minimal for temperature, DO, nitrate, and nitrite, while higher errors occurred for organic nitrogen and phosphorus, reflecting the complexity of nutrient dynamics. Root mean square error (RMSE) values were within acceptable ranges for most parameters, although wet-season temperature exceeded the 0.5 °C benchmark, highlighting a limitation in model performance under variable flow conditions (Table 6).

According to [5] and [7], a well calibrated model should have RMSE values below 0.5 for water quality parameters. In this study, most RMSE values met this benchmark, confirming satisfactory calibration and validation of the model.

Table 6. RMSE table Showing Values for various water quality parameters.

Parameter	RMSE Dry Season	RMSE Wet Season
Temperature	0.401	0.044
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	0.133	0.0467
Organic Nitrogen (N)	0.0002338	0.0003311
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	0.00577	0.00092
Nitrite (NO ₂ ⁻)	0.01479	0.00491
Organic Phosphorus (P)	0.04254	0.0088

4. 5. Statistical Summary of Water Quality Parameters

Across all stations, mean DO values ranged between 4.30 and 4.61 mg/L, consistently below the 6.5 mg/L ecological threshold. Nitrate and nitrogen remained within WHO (2007) drinking water standards, while nitrite (>0.2 mg/L) and phosphorus (>0.05 mg/L) exceeded limits at nearly all stations.

The highest phosphorus level was recorded at Emir’s Road (1.125 mg/L), far above the eutrophication threshold. These results confirm persistent oxygen depletion and nutrient enrichment across the Asa River.

Table 7. Summary of maximum, minimum, and mean values of selected water quality parameters at four sampling stations along Asa River compared with WHO (2007) standards.

Station	Statistical value	Temp (°C)	DO (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Nitrogen (mg/L)	Phosphorus (mg/L)
Asa Dam	Maximum	29.1	4.8	0.481	0.231	0.0168	1.060
	Minimum	27.6	3.8	0.055	0.220	0.0027	0.555
	Mean	28.6	4.30	0.268	0.225	0.0098	0.805
Unity	Maximum	29.2	5.2	0.466	0.271	0.0056	1.080
	Minimum	28.0	3.8	0.070	0.258	0.0022	0.125
	Mean	28.6	4.54	0.266	0.265	0.0039	0.604
Emir’s Rd	Maximum	29.2	5.0	0.459	0.275	0.0056	1.125
	Minimum	27.5	3.86	0.059	0.223	0.0022	0.040
	Mean	28.4	4.45	0.258	0.249	0.0039	0.583
Amilegbe	Maximum	29.2	4.9	0.462	0.257	0.0028	1.110
	Minimum	27.8	4.4	0.065	0.206	0.0022	0.050
	Mean	28.6	4.61	0.262	0.229	0.0025	0.581
WHO Standard (2007)	–	≤ 30	≥ 6.5	≤ 50	≤ 0.2	≤ 10	≤ 0.05
Compliance	–	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study applied a coupled hydrodynamic–water quality model using HEC-RAS to assess the pollution status of the Asa River in Ilorin, Nigeria. The model successfully reproduced depth, velocity, and key water quality parameters across four monitoring stations during both dry and wet seasons. Persistent oxygen depletion was observed, with dissolved oxygen ranging from 3.9 to 5.2 mg/L, consistently below the 6.5 mg/L ecological threshold. Nutrient analysis revealed that while nitrate levels were within WHO (2007) standards, nitrite (>0.2 mg/L) and phosphorus (>0.05 mg/L) exceeded permissible limits, creating a high risk of eutrophication.

Model calibration and validation showed close agreement between observed and simulated data, with minor deviations for organic nitrogen and phosphorus. These findings confirm that the Asa River is under ecological stress and is unsuitable for direct domestic or recreational use without treatment.

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